

Trip Report: Shiprock & Barringer Crater

Electrogeological Morphology of the Shiprock and Attempts to Calculate the likelihood of EDM origins of The “Meteor Crater,” with retrospective analysis of present material knowledge and comparison of hypotheses.

Sf. R. Careaga, MSTOM, BSEE

On behalf of The Electric Pulse (thinktank)

This paper must be viewed at <https://bit.ly/3x5fxWf> in order to see all evidence

June 2022

Synopsis

The author made site visits to Shiprock and Barringer Crater, among others, in May 2022. The purpose of these was for sightseeing and exploration of on the ground facts. In Part 1 of this report, the author will show that Shiprock is the most unambiguous electrogeology and catastrophic cryptoexplosive event on record, with a near 0 possibility of stratigraphic or volcanic origin. The author will also cite references to standard geological sampling and show image and videographic evidence, as well as present logical issues and propose a method for properly dating the site.

In part 2, the author will weigh the pros and cons for the two origin possibilities of Barringer Crater: Shoemaker’s kinetic (bolide) cryptoexplosive event, and the Thornhill-Steinbacher (and Hall) theory of electric discharge machining. The author will attempt to more succinctly define the precise origin, if possible.

In Part 3 the author will compare and contrast the two sites, as well as differences with volcanic morphology within the desert southwest, which is home to a wide variety of volcanism. More proposals for differentiation will be provided as well.

Synopsis	1
Part 1 - Shiprock, New Mexico	3
KILLING OF THE GREAT BIRD	20
Part 2 - Barringer Crater	23
Table 1 - Electrogeological Catastrophic Morphology	24
Evidence of EDM at Barringer Crater	25
Regarding Tektites and Shocked Diamond spherules:	27
Part 3 - Southwest Volcanism vs. Hall's Arc-Blasted Earth Hypothesis	30
Capulin Cinder Cone and Surrounding Volcanic Field	32
Arizona Snowbowl and Sunset Crater (San Francisco Volcanic Field)	34
Valles Caldera	35
Ute Mountain Region	36
Springerfield Volcanic Field	37
Shiprock - Clearly lacking an important component...	38
Electro-volcanism	38
Mars	38
Io	40
Enceladus	41
Venus	41
Mercury and the Moon	42
Lightning in Plumes	43
Hall Theory & Combined Morphologies	44
Canary Islands, Living Examples of Solar Forcing?	48
Shiprock vs. Barringer Crater	49
Conclusions	50
References	51

Part 1 - Shiprock, New Mexico

Shiprock is listed as a “volcanic neck” (monadnock¹) or “central feeder pipe” of a larger volcanic landform which has since eroded away, exposing breccia and thin “veins” of lava.² This is very obviously patently false, and the author will show this, as well as elaborate on the Navajo myths. Its proposed age is 27 million years, and from base to top is 1,583 feet (482.5 m) in height, with a total altitude of 7,177 feet (2,188 m).³ It is, quite demonstrably **not** that old, and I will show that with local eratta there is obvious evidence the site is no more than 13,000 years, probably less.

But first, there are a series of figures that are needed:

Figure 1 - Shiprock’s “main vein”, clearly not a lavatube⁴ and as will be shown, not rooted. Above material is a semi-obsidian, iron filled brecca, like stone-glass. Note the distinct lack of strewn boulders along the main (those on the right have been partially knocked down by humans), the pileup of dune and dirt, and what one

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/science/monadnock>

² <https://geoinfo.nmt.edu/tour/landmarks/shiprock/home.html>

³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shiprock>

⁴ Which are hollow; https://volcanoes.usgs.gov/vsc/glossary/lava_tube.html

cannot see here: high winds. This angle isn't good, either, but there is a measurable pulse/amplitude along the vein. We use that word here, cautiously, as we are not implying a magma/lava vein but an electrical tendril.

Figure 2 - Here we see one of the two main sections of boulder eratta; this is the smaller and more natural of the two deposits. We can clearly see what the erosion rate would be, without human interference, in most sections where wind is forced to concentrate. The theory here would be that the egg-like electrical behavior in the center indicates a slightly different formation morphology leading to more crumbly material. But the material is atop of the soil, which is highly loose and susceptible to erosion.

Figure 3 - The sinusoidal behavior of the vein is both horizontal and vertical. Note that though the vein leans right, there is not as significantly greater a distribution of boulders than other areas. In fact, the author conjectures that the decay rate of these normal vein regions could be used, with satellite tracking, to determine a near exact estimation of age in reverse by looking backwards upon the decay rate. Even with climate changes, the average wind flux through the veins should be similar over a ten year period.

Figure 4 - horizontal, and not vertical, polarized stratigraphy; similar as per Garden of the Gods, next to Hicks' Dome, Illinois.⁵; the left material is easily crumbled by the right (limestone), and feels like petrified mud.

⁵ With it magnetic, and not gravitic anomaly:

https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

More importantly the “mud” is what is beneath the Vein’s basalt, and not the limestone. Yes, the softer material is *beneath* the supposed “lava tube”. It is highly erodible, as well.

Figure 5 - Occasional fossil shapes, unknown origins, fill in the supposed magma. Andy Hall (and Neil Thompson) describes these cavitations as electrical events of expulsion and sputtering of discharge.⁶

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPcF40vBqzs>

Figure 6 - a better view of polar behavior: note the vein on the upper right corner, and sudden increase in iron

Figures 7-10: display of wild layering that clearly defies stratigraphy, uplift hypotheses, and demonstrates clear crystalline formation. Interspersed within the “basalt” (breccia) is the sand/mud petrification, as if built like bricks in a wall. Indeed the opposite side of this formation has a strange Inca-like appearance. But there is no archaeological evidence for anything other than a natural formation, and this backside photograph supports this. The polar behavior is common in electrogeological morphology. This formation is behaving as an anode like AC event, while the “Meteor Crater” - if electrogeological - would possibly be a DC cathode event.

Figure 11 - Author along backside of vein - relative to the parked car - not the removed “basalt” vein, exposing a limestone and petrified mud bed, and not a bed of magma. Note the scale of this vein increases sloping up to the Shiprock, where there is a sudden vertical expulsion. There are also nearby structures like the Shiprock which point back to its center, perhaps indicating multiple fingers of connection

Figure 12 (below) - the vertical front face of the stone, versus the gentle slope on the backside. Natural errata had no apparent increase front or back, excepting the human strewn field (of course) and the aforementioned area noted in Figure 2

Figure 13 - Typical New Mexico mesa and plateau stratigraphy, potential volcanic origins. Again boulder errata suggested as a means to measure age.

Figure 14 (below) - extremely loamy (despite being dry) soil-sand mix, very soft. Mixture with obsidian basalts and with organic materials noted; the soil should be gone after millions of years, replaced with rock and sand only. Either more sand than shown (a nominal amount, perhaps thousands of years) in Figure 1, or less overall and more stone.

Studies⁷ reveal a shocking number of mineral resources; which also supports a transmutation event hypothesis. There are also Uranium⁸ evaporate deposits⁹, which reminds us of Australia with its high tektite occurrence. This type of radiation¹⁰ is, in our opinion in EPEMC, more evidence of an energetic, not kinetic event.

⁷ https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/Internet/FSE_MANUSCRIPTS/new_mexico/NM717/0/Shiprock.pdf

⁸ <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/6075949>

⁹ https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/2016/05/f31/AST_S13437.pdf

¹⁰ <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1025/ML102560402.pdf>

Figure 15 - "back side" of pictured break. Perhaps human induced, after all? Boulders are, again, surprisingly few for millions of years. Winds were ~ 10 knots magnitude.

Looking at the Google Earth images:

Figure 16 - Shiprock formation (orthogonal), with veins coming in at direct angles, and yet the main vein in study does not approach directly. Asymmetry is a hallmark of electrical processes in space on Earth. Note also in all vein photographs sudden breaks in “tube” vectors, making one wonder why would a fluid suddenly change track and then go back *towards* the destination, over and over? If it flowed out *from* the formation, that would make a little more sense. Also that the veins suddenly decrease in altitude just prior to conjoining at the formation is suspicious. Mining? Doesn't seem apparent from these images.

Figure 17 - Comparison of human boulder field and broken section, and unusually low erosive evidence. General average boulder migration can be seen on back and front sides. Under human mined region (top of image) the lack of basalt is noted and limestone made more obvious. Also in center the same core petrified mud flow. As seen in last figure below, animation shows how easily destroyed this material is: it surely could not contain magma!

Figure 18 - Sudden increased erosion in this region of vein. Slightly high terrain may indicate fog condensation or other processes at work; note that the main drainage system is on the left, however, while the largest escarpment is on the right (not man made). There may also be a polar difference in material, or winds may prevail in such a way that looser sand accumulates on the right than the left; both sides indicate this is not millions of years of erosion, but thousands. This type of material could easily erode as shown in a short period of time. Again, note the rhythmic break in vein “flow” and immediate return to the mean.

Figure 19 - [Breaking petrified mud easily](#)

The author feels strongly that the greatest weight of evidence is not for a typical volcanic origin, but electrogeological morphology. Let us now examine the myths surround Shiprock, by the

Navajo descendents of the archaics that observed it, and made such civilizations as the Pueblo, who build cities underneath of cliffs and maybe in caves:

*“...When the people first emerged from the lower world, they had seen a **Yeh** over on Mount Taylor, Tson-tsilth, but he was small and they were not afraid. Now they saw him again, and **he had grown very large and had a very big nose, small eyes, and black whiskers on his chin**. They realized that he had [p. 70](#) turned into a giant. When they first saw him, they thought he was a Yeh but now they knew that he was a Yehtso or Big Giant. (The reason that the giant lived on Tsoll-tsilth was because Tsoll-tsilth was a badly behaved mountain which had argued about its name and had asked to dress in white shell beads). The **Sun claimed the giant and called him his son**, although he really was not related to him, and the Sun took the giant to his home and dressed him with stone shoes and clothing of Bezh or obsidian to protect him from his enemies. And he gave him **the Lightning Arrow** (Iknee-kah) as a weapon **for his right hand**, and a stone knife for his left hand. When he had dressed him, the **Sun took the Yehtso on a streak of lightning and went to Tsoll-tsilth**. The giant had a hot spring, Toh-sit-toh, from which he drank, and though the people lived far from this place, when the giant would call “singo,” the people were forced to come to him, and then he would eat them.*

...

*There was an enormous bird, Tseh-nah-hahleh, who lived at Ship Rock, Tseh-ed-ah, who had a very long beak, very large eyes, and **his claws were very long and sharp**, and he ate people. He had two little ones in his nest whom he had to feed.*

There also was a man made of stone who lay stretched out on a hill beside the river just west of the Aztec Ruins. When anyone walked past he would kick them into the San Juan River, [p. 71](#) and when they were drowned, he would feed them to his two children. He was called Tseh-ed-ah-eh-delklithy, which means Kicking Rock. His children lived in the river and ate the drowned people.

Also on the top of the Jemez Mountains there was a great hollow place called Nechochee-otso, and there lived a great striped rock which could roll very quickly in any direction, and killed people by rolling on them. It was called Tseh-nagi, Rolling Rock.

*Then on the east side of Blue Water, New Mexico, there was a red mountain where a lot of black insects lived who killed people by looking at them. **They stared at a person until he was paralyzed, and then they ate him**. They were called Benan-yah-runi, or Staring-Eyes-That-Kill.*

*Where the La Plata River meets the San Juan River lived an **immense centipede who was very fierce and treacherous, and could run very fast**.¹¹ He had many young ones who helped to eat the people. He was called Sil-dil-hushy-tso, the One-Who-Bites.*

...

KILLING OF THE GREAT BIRD

Next day he clothed himself in stone armor and asked his mother and grandmother where he could find the Great Bird, Tseh-nah-hahleh. And his mother told him that it was very dangerous to hunt the

¹¹ Quite possibly a reference to Step Potential: https://www.academia.edu/69494984/Plasmaglyphs_Part_4

bird. Nayenezgani, however, started on his way, taking with him the skin of the Dah-il-kadeh, and **the blood enclosed in the monster's stomach, and the earth shook as he went. The rainbow carried him towards the home of the Great Bird on top of Ship Rock.** Before he reached it, he dressed himself in the skin of the Dah-il-kadeh, and he carried the monster's stomach full of blood inside his clothing. The [p. 90](#) Great Bird saw him coming, and flew towards him making much noise, flying over him **four times.** Then she caught up Nayenezgani in her claws and carried him to Ship Rock, circling it four times and then threw him down between the two peaks. Nayenezgani would have been killed by the fall except for the fact that **the feather which the Spider Woman had given him enabled him to fall slowly.**

When he lit (sic) on the rock, he tore open the stomach full of blood, and the Great Bird thought she had killed him, and so flew off the nest telling her little ones to eat Nayenezgani, as he was dead. Nayenezgani lay still, and the little birds came nearer to him, but he said: "Sh-sh," and frightened them away. They called out to their mother: "Shemah (Mother), this human being is not dead, for he said 'Sh-sh' to us," but the Great Bird said: "That is nonsense, go on and eat. The noise you heard was the sound of his fall." So the Great Bird flew away to the west over the mountains and when she had gone Nayenezgani got up and went to their nest and called the little birds to him, and they were frightened and went back to their nest and began to cry. Nayenezgani told them to be quiet, and that if they made a noise, he would kill them.

The oldest bird came to him and Nayenezgani took hold of him and pushed his beak down, and made his wings a different shape, and painted his wings and tail white and told him to go south and live there and be good, and not do any harm to any one any more, and he became the first eagle. Nayenezgani called the smaller bird to him four times before he would come, and then Nayenezgani gave him a long pair of ears and told him that he was to be the owl, and that if he harmed the earth people he would kill him. And he sent him north to the La Plata Mountains to a place which was to be his home, called Saltahn-iskai, near Pagosa Peak. And the owl was very tired when he reached his new home.

Nayenezgani looked about to find a place in which to hide so [p. 91](#) that he could kill the parent birds, but the only place he could find was in the nest, and so he hid there. Then the **male rain** started, and he saw the father bird flying back with something in his claws and when he came nearer, Nayenezgani saw that he was carrying a handsome young man who was dressed in fine jewelry and many bracelets. And the bird dropped the man, and when he fell the turquoise jewelry flew in every direction. The father bird then lit on the peak, but before he folded his wings, Nayenezgani shot him and saw that the young man whom the bird had dropped on the peak was a Taos Indian. From the west began a light female rain, and the mother bird flew in, carrying a young and pretty girl dressed in white shell beads. And she dropped the girl on the rock. Just as the mother bird lit on the peak, Nayenezgani shot her with a lightning arrow and the bird fell dead from the peak.

Nayenezgani now looked about to find a way down from the peak, and below he saw a bat whose name was Jahbunny-estsan (Bat Woman), and he said to her: "Grandmother, help me down, and I will give you a feather." She hid four times and would not answer. Finally she told him to go to the other side of the peak, and then she appeared to Nayenezgani with a basket on her back, upheld by spider webs. She danced about when she reached the top of the peak and said to him: "Now get into my

basket,” but Nayenezgani answered: “The strings are too small, they will break under my weight,” but she said: “**No, I can carry very heavy load with these webs.**”

Nayenezgani was afraid and would not get into the basket, so the Bat Woman told him to fill it with big rocks and he did so, and the strings of the spider web still held, although they buzzed with the strain. Nayenezgani was convinced that the Bat Woman could carry him, and he took the stones out of the basket, and went over to the edge of the peak and got into the basket. The Bat Woman told him to shut his eyes, and she began to go down. Half way down the Bat woman stopped on a [p. 92](#) small ledge and walked back and forth while Nayenezgani wondered whether they were on the ground or not, but he could not see as she had told him to keep his eyes shut.

He grew so nervous that he opened his eyes, and at once they both fell to the ground, but fortunately the shelf on which they had been was not far up the cliff. The Bat Woman was so angry that she struck Nayenezgani with a cane she held in her hand, because he had opened his eyes. Then he got out of the basket and went to where the Great Bird had fallen. He pulled out twelve of his tail feathers, doing the same to the female bird, and he scalped both birds with his stone knife, and told the Bat Woman to help herself to the feathers that remained, and she filled her basket with small feathers.

Nayenezgani warned her not to go through the sunflower place as she would regret it; and he set off towards home, but as he went, he watched the Bat Woman because he saw she was going straight to the sunflower place. When she reached there, all the feathers in the basket blew out, and she lost them all. She went back to find the dead birds again, thinking that she would find more feathers, but Nayenezgani did not wait to see if she got any. He mounted his rainbow and went home, where his return was celebrated in the same way as it had been before.”¹² (emphasis added)

There are other stories with references to the twin warriors (Jupiter and Saturn). And there is this synopsis:

“The Winged Monster, also known as the Great Bird or Monster Eagle (Tsé Nináhálééh), was one of those menacing beings. Most accounts tell of a **giant bird** who lived in Ship Rock (Tsé Bit’a’i), a landmark monolith in the Navajo homeland, located in northwestern New Mexico. The bird was very powerful and **could lift people up in the air and throw them** against the rocks in order to kill and then eat them. Monster Slayer, who had a **magic feather** which enabled him to survive the Winged Monster’s attack, managed to trick the bird, destroy it, and tame its two young chicks, transforming them into **an eagle** and **an owl**. The geologic formation of Shiprock itself is also believed to be the body of the great monster layed out on the ground, with the two ridgelines extending away from the peak marking the beast’s outstretched wings.”¹³ (sic)

Looking across the myths and particularly the bolded sections, we see some worldwide motifs and archetypes; and a few we will see relevant to the Three Rivers Petroglyphs trip report.

1. Yeh, perhaps a reference to the worldwide God-sound (Ywahoo, Yahweh, Yao, IAO).
2. Probably plasma trails on approaching bodies moving as *like a comet* around Sol (possibly Monster Slayer).
3. The Giant being Shamash, the Sun being Sol.

¹² <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/nav/ncm/ncm4.htm>

¹³ <https://ehillerman.unm.edu/node/2255#sthash.urDizEDM.dpbs>

4. The Lightning Arrow is an analogous reference to Brahma's Arrow, and Brahma is associated with Jupiter (Indra with Saturn); this is reflective of Odin and Zeus.
5. Claws have been shown in Chinese plasmaglyphics to refer to the star and its extended trident lightning "thunderbolts".
6. The reference to paralysis and insects here could be literal, but more likely are references to therianthropes and electrical effects. They remind us of Lot's wife, as well.
7. We see that some giant planetary body moved by, probably Shamash's planets proto-Saturn or proto-Jupiter as references to intestines remind us of the Enki and the World Order and other intestines in the "tree" motifs. But moreover the rainbow makes its appearance, and a "rainbow road" of course is a famous Nordic myth of the Gods' bridge. It appears to be a plasma bridge that was multicolored in the EDIN in the sky.
8. Multiple references to feathers (light weight? Ladder pinches and synchrotrons?) and lightness, to webs (probably a reference to the invisible electric force), and catching people who are thrown (or could jump high?).
 - a. This only makes sense during the Jovian era (Megalithic Period's core temporal aspect)
9. Male rain might be a euphemism for mana (white like semen).
10. Buzzing with strains sounds like electrification.
11. The giant bird is a worldwide motif, but we are reminded of Zhuangzi (Chuang Tsu's) "tai peng".
12. The eagle and owl appear to be direct references to a plasma electric sheet formation and the owl itself to the twin warrior-brothers just post Shamash breakup. This is covered elsewhere.

Part 2 - Barringer Crater

There are numerous objections to Mr. Shoemaker's conclusions¹⁴, and the bolide hypothesis. Bolides are *not* impossible, though they are unusual due to friction and electric explosion events (airbursts, but not completely thermal, like Tunguska). The main issue this author has is with Shoemaker's overall assertion, rather lamely, that impact events are "the most fundamental planetary process"¹⁵ or cosmic rocky bodies experience. This is patently **false** as plasma-electromagnetism is by far the most fundamental, and after that gravity, kinetics, momentum, optical issues like absorption and reflectivity, comes next. Each of these is PEMF related. But yes, bolide strikes do happen. However, there are no other known examples the author can think of that are perfectly orthogonal. In brief here are the main objections:

- Orthogonal strike
- No bow shock
- Shallow
- Edge scalloping
- Octagonal (asymmetric)
- Lack of shattered fragments < 800m below surface (and some have asserted even 100 ft!)
- Lack of direct meteorological fragment evidence¹⁶

¹⁴ <https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/1959/0108/report.pdf>

¹⁵ <https://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0406368> "According to Shoemaker, the "impact of solid bodies is the most fundamental process that has taken place on the terrestrial planets"

False.

¹⁶ In fact the museum there makes frequent use of correlative evidence, with references to other events, and has an extensive educational center. It is delightful, even if it may be wrong. Certainly it is worth the admission price.

There are many other potential ‘cons’ to the bold strike hypothesis. The number one of these being the lack of energetic evidence. If you have a crater that is forcibly ejected to the width that is seen, you would expect a correspondingly deep trench and an absolutely devastating area surrounding the region. Whereas J. Gable’s crater electric experiments have shown very clearly that electrical discharges can excavate correspondingly wide + shallow polygonal craters within short **direct arc** bursts. There appear to be eight main electrogeological formations:

Table 1 - Electrogeological Catastrophic Morphology

<i>Type</i>	<i>Proposed Example(s)</i>	<i>Proposed Scale or Origin</i>
Direct Arc Discharge	Barringer? Hudson Bay craters	Enki and Enlil
Perattian Thunderbolt (56 rays)	Big Sink, KY	Jovian <i>induced</i>
Anode Uplift and conical hills	Ayer’s, Pilot knobs, Stone Mtn, Devil’s Tower	Shamash or Neptune Arc
Lichtenburg (anode or cathode)	Knobs of KY, Grand Canyon	Jovian or Venus
Rilles	Lunar rilles (non-tectonic)	Earth-Moon arc
Cathode (center leaning) mountains	Wudang mountains, Black Hills, SD, three rivers NM region	Shamash
Domes	Upheaval Dome, Central KY, Half-dome ¹⁷	Electric Field? Direct arc?
Electroexplosive Airburst Events	Hick’s Dome, Melbourne comet (1491), Wales	Mega to gigatons TNT

There are other proposed morphologies, such as Shiprock, or various arches, etc. But they probably are parts of the larger main categories, or combination events. For example, we don’t know AC vs. DC during the arc discharges, and if they are not single bursts like Big Sink, are there more permanent connections? The answer is yes, but we have yet to understand the rules for this behavior on a ‘permanent’ level.

The key issue for the electrogeological morphology (the cons), especially in terms of Barringer Crater, are more or less a lack of data and knowledge beyond some basic observation and simple lab experiments. And, very weak data on controls and experimental setup.¹⁸ We don’t know the exact means for things like instant petrification¹⁹, but we do see the strong evidence for electric discharge machining (EDM). Others have noted these on Earth and Mars²⁰. The author has covered the extensive evidence and reasoning for it to be on the Moon²¹, as well as mythological testimony of direct connections between the Earth and Moon²².

We also know from lab experiment that:

- Changes can occur quickly, as is suggested in the Psalms and Exodus.
- They leave shocked rock and diamond dust.

¹⁷ First formed, then cut in half by glaciers

¹⁸ I.e. highly compelling “garage science”

¹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5vOMGQTjW9k>

²⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

²¹ https://www.academia.edu/69494987/Appendix_A_and_B_Plates pp. 159-176

²² https://www.academia.edu/69494984/Plasmaglyphs_Part_4

- The shapes can be polygonal of many types and do not have to leave a bowshock, though uplift can and does occur.
- The forces are incredibly intense, but can leave other structures nearby relatively unaffected²³.
- Transmutation of minerals is commonplace
- Aging schemes will cease to work *if* there is isotopic sequestration due to re-arrangement of nuclear mass and breakdown or buildup of neutron bonding
- Energy levels are highly scalable

In the case of the latter point, we can see that even simple magnetospheric and plasmaspheric induction, due to the rubbing of Earth's magneto and electrospheric circuits with another body, or direct magnetic tunneling with the sun (and "solar forcing"²⁴) can introduce vast amounts of joules to the Earth system rapidly, even without arc breakdown of free space. Sort of a "dark mode" plasma mediated event. Also electric fields themselves might introduce extremely powerful circumstances for electrodynamic and kinetic changes on the planet. For example, at the Middlesboro crater there is a bow shock evidence for impact, but a wider "crooked smile"²⁵ (Hall) formation of triangular etching of Pine Mountain, nearby. The coincidence of this cannot be accidental, but causative.

If the crater is not a direct EDM excavation, then the bolide was clearly **attracted** to the spot by the formation mechanism. This, too, the Jephtha Knob bolide may have been attracted to the Kentucky Dome, just as the Fort Knox upheaval dome lies in the Knobs region which surrounds the giant Kentucky Dome. That the Hicks Dome^{26 27} is nearby in the Kentuckiana region, and that this is latero-recumbent to the Land Between the Lakes gorges, as well as proximal to the world's largest fluorspar deposits²⁸, is a little too convenient. At Hicks Dome, of course, there are strong examples of liesegang banding²⁹ and stone polarization³⁰, and the Hicks Dome has a bow shock, and yet only has a magnetic anomaly and not a gravitic one (so volcanism is out!)

The main point being that the pros of the electrogeological morphology often outweigh the cons, and demand far more inspection. The pros for keeping standard cryptoexplosive bolide theories, of course, are simplicity, ease of explanation, ease of education, not having to change textbooks, etc. But the primary impediment is likely to be the commercialization of the location. Its business snake is "Meteor Crater." There is literally a "vested" interest.

Evidence of EDM at Barringer Crater

Let's take a look at the EDM evidence, and speculate or even free-associate about what is seen:

²³ In one documented case the electricity "glued" mammoth feet to the ground, while their bodies were blasted away with high winds.

²⁴ <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/11/4/044013>

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdfBGqWpW5w>

²⁶ <https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/1974/0157/report.pdf>

²⁷ <https://pubs.usgs.gov/pp/0970/report.pdf>

²⁸ <https://pubs.usgs.gov/pp/1538g/report.pdf>

²⁹ <https://shawneenf.oncell.com/en/24-garden-of-the-gods-bizarre-bands-55873.html>

³⁰ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge pp.8

Figure 20 - Barringer Crater, nearly orthogonal view; credit: wiki

Moving around the circles clockwise from the largest:

1. We see perfectly straight - impossibly straight - angular changes, in a distinct overall octagonal pattern, and this reminds us of the proof that the Northern hemisphere was definitely, without a doubt exposed to direct visual contact with the northern pole of Jupiter. That is a statistical and historical fact.
2. Scalloping, a common feature as arcs (called arc because of their shape) rotate around the edges at the end of the discharge.
3. More scalloping and sharp edges
4. More angular and asymmetric formation
5. The best example of scalloping, and a clear defiance of a kinetic explosion (which would be radially even in distribution).

Figure 21 - Isometric view; credit: history.com

Here we see the very obvious shallowness, but also the cuboidal rather than conical nature of the crater is more obvious. Some will claim “infill”, and there is definitely that. However, they are only pointing out a larger problem: the age proposed of this even means it has far too little erosion to be possible for this crater, in the author’s opinion. Note, also, the general lack of destroyed material around the crater, and distinct lack of bow shock, as compared to Jephtha Knob, Middlesboro, and the Yucatan crater. These facts are covered in many of the author’s other works and slideshow presentations.

Figure 22 - 40’ Rille formed by a single lightning bolt on a baseball field, Oklahoma³¹

Regarding Tektites and Shocked Diamond spherules:

It is widely publicized that *only* nuclear and meteoric blasts have the power to create shocked nanodiamond dust and tektites³². This is false as it is also known to happen with relatively low but high temperature events such as lightning or even volcanic blasts of VEI-7+ varieties. However, the fact that lightning is capable of creating transmutations and rilles, and the fact that electrogeology proposes means for much more epic blasts than standard volcanism (via even electrovolcanism) eliminates this requirement altogether. In fact it *blasts through it*, as it were, as the energy levels are not comparable. Even a simple Perattian single-pulse thunderbolt, like our “smoking gun” at Big Sink, is 5x-15x stronger than the Bikini

³¹ <https://www.ldsforum.com/viewtopic.php?t=17155&start=30>

³² <https://www.britannica.com/science/tektite>

Hydrogen bomb, itself a 15 megaton blast. This, the author maintains, is a **small event**, in the grand scheme. Barringer, is also a relatively small event, although it represents a more continuous arc and ‘pumping’ of charge between the larger and smaller bodies of Jupiter and the Earth. Jupiter’s magnetosphere is presently 26,000x stronger than Earth’s, and there is reason to suspect it was much stronger 4-7kya (our lower and upper limits for the caps of the Jovian era). Nevertheless, even still a small location like Barringer, as compared with larger continuous discharges, such as the upper 2/3 of the Grand Canyon, or the Devil’s Tower anode, or the Ayer’s Rock event (which possibly brought so much Uranium and tektite to the Australian continent,) is very important to discuss. Rather than be a detractor from the theory, it is a bolster to it, because it supports the native origin myths. As noted elsewhere by the author, natives have no reason to lie, though they have every reason to anthropomorphize these events. Especially after the gods ‘vanish’ from the sky.

Figure 23 - Map at the Meteor Crater museum/learning center

“Tektite is not really a gemstone--it's a form of natural glass (much like obsidian) caused by heat. Rather than the heat being from volcanos, however, the heat that makes tektite comes

from atmospheric friction. Meteorites enter the planet's atmosphere and are pulled down by gravity--the friction caused by moving through the atmosphere at hundreds of miles per hour builds up heat in the meteorite. When the meteorite impacts, it spends that heat energy (and usually itself) into the local rocks. This causes the rocks to melt with the remains of the meteorite, creating tektites."³³ (sic)

Note that electricity easily exceeds frictional heat; although all heat is electromagnetic.

Figure 24 - Shoemaker's diagram at the museum; note the deepest probes are nowhere near the 3000 m proposed for meteoric fragments, which seems to be a priori. The vast amount of breccia seems to better indicate high energy, but we actually don't know the shape because the sampling is done vertically in the center.

³³ <https://www.firemountaingems.com/resources/encyclopedia/gem-notes/ha5r>

Part 3 - Southwest Volcanism vs. Hall's Arc-Blasted Earth Hypothesis

The southwest is definitely volcanic, and there are plenty of examples of standard “tectonic” or “magma-plume” volcanoes. The problem is that this is not necessarily contraindicated or exclusionary for electrovolcanism, nor does Andy Hall eliminate the former while embracing the latter³⁴. However, one cannot seriously consider the geology of the southwest desert, without observing the difficulty of explaining formations *without* catastrophism. For much of this, the reader is encouraged to review the entire corpus of videos by Hall³⁵, starting with his iconic “Arc-blasted Earth”³⁶ presentation at the Electric Universe conference. Beyond that, the author will assume there is a basic understanding of the ‘permanent’ (now gone) electrovortex or cyclone³⁷ (ala Jovian or Saturnian) hovering over the southwest desert. There are interesting identifying clues and unique keys, which cannot be explained with upthrust, stratigraphy, or fluvial and wind erosion. Therefore we consider this evidence, as well as the overall correlation, and compare and contrast the two main sites along with other typical, or atypical, volcanism. Atypical would exclude Shiprock, for as the author showed, this is not a volcanic site, but a high temperature anode arc uplift event, and the veins are not lava tubes but sinusoidal ripples which transmuted iron layers, lifting them up into sand to make obsidian-like breccia, leaving behind purer metrified mud underneath, bordered by limestone on each side. And it did this *recently*.

However, before discussing, there needs to be a reminder to the reader that we have each of these three key parts:

1. Direct knowledge of birkeland current connections from Jupiter to Io³⁸ (high volcanism), Saturn to Enceladus³⁹ (cryovolcanism⁴⁰), and the Sun to the Earth (“magnetic tunnels” or “flux ropes”)⁴¹. This is non-controversial Standard

³⁴ The author doesn't speak for Mr. Hall; but it seems unlikely Andy is against all tectonic theories.

³⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/a-hall>

³⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>

³⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LsltU6getrY>

³⁸ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1700040>

³⁹ <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/resources/15289/electrical-circuit-between-saturn-and-enceladus/> Figure 25- Cassini

⁴⁰ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4020-9217-6_21 Figure 26 - water plumes on Enceladus / Cassini

⁴¹ <https://www.physics.ucla.edu/plasma-exp/references/publications/PhysScripta/ITCPP99rls1preprint.pdf>

Model astronomy. The best explanations come out of the Wiley/AGU100 text, “Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond.”⁴²

2. Examples of vortical storms on large gas giants, related to electric currents.⁴³
 - a. Most recently Saturn and Jupiter reconnecting and the south pole of Jupiter going from 5 to 6 vortices⁴⁴ as the two headed to the 2020 conjunction⁴⁵; observed November 3 2019.⁴⁶
3. Examples of highly electric ash plumes, and the ‘correlation’ of solar re-awakening and massive eruptions at La Palma, in September 2021.

In other words, suspend disbelief, if only for the moment to consider Hall’s extraordinary proposal. Essentially it is this: that during a not so archaic past, connections between Earth and the nearby gas giants / gods, enabled high energy semi-permanent energy sources with the Earth. This differs from the present EPEMC Shamash hypothesis⁴⁷, but it is not impossible. It seems overly unified, when to the author many of these events appear like different periods of the Earth’s formation, based on energy footprint (size). But there are many ways to skin the cat, so to speak. Nevertheless, let’s look at *obvious* examples of traditional volcanism in the southwest:

1. Cinder Cones
2. Shield Volcanoes (and associated lava fields)
3. Calderas and Volcanic fields

We will contrast this with the maars⁴⁸ and other examples of ‘magma’ plugs that sit atop conical hills. This is important for potentially understanding the motivation of the natives to use the particular hill of the Three Rivers Petroglyphs. More to the point, we can draw upon a compare/contrast of that site (in the other Trip Report) with the Great Serpent Mound cryptoexplosive site in Ohio.⁴⁹

⁴² <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Electric+Currents+in+Geospace+and+Beyond-p-9781119324492>

⁴³ The author has shown this in numerous papers; recommend re-read of “Magnetic Universe Theory,” https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

See also the works of Donald Scott and Wal Thornhill from “The Electric Sky” to “The Electric Universe” books.

⁴⁴ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/nasas-juno-navigators-enable-jupiter-cyclone-discovery>

⁴⁵ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/the-great-conjunction-of-jupiter-and-saturn>

⁴⁶ And covered as being correlative and highly infamous with COVID-19; see:

<https://www.nasa.gov/feature/the-great-conjunction-of-jupiter-and-saturn>

⁴⁷

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

⁴⁸ <https://volcanoes.usgs.gov/vsc/glossary/maar.html>

⁴⁹ Possibly the actual site of the thunderbolt strike that killed megafauna at Big Bone Lick, KY and elsewhere!

Capulin Cinder Cone and Surrounding Volcanic Field

Figure 27 - Capulin Monument and surrounding area; credit: Google

The lower right mountain is the parent mountain, a shield volcano of comparatively low height / diameter (as compared to Mt. Fuji or Mt. Shasta), perhaps indicating a lower energy (compared to Mauna Loa or Krakatoa) magma-plume. But the effect is the same. The rupture at the Jose Butte released thick > 50 feet in height lava fields, and the Capulin cinder cone⁵⁰ had its own shallower fields. Similarly the Horseshoe Crater has this, only it is apparently much younger, and the vegetation has not managed to get a foothold in this region. That *may* indicate an electrovolcanic result, perhaps iron in the dead plume attracted the activity. But in general what we see is clear diffuse activity with periodic buildup, and potentially dangerous. This is a younger field than, say, the Valles Caldera, and probably indicates a newer field. Or, at least, more tired.

Regarding Maars, they appear to be like cinder cones, however lack the obvious crater in the center which makes typical cinders like Capulin, so iconic. Maars like are found in Mexico, are also either examples of the same moving arc sputtering discharge as formed the knobs region of Kentucky... or really are volcanic fields.

⁵⁰ A one-off, short lived volcano surrounded by ash and killed by being plugged with its own lava

Figure 28 - Maars of Pinacate; a volcanic field? Or grand example of EDM? (as per Hall); credit: Daily Plasma⁵¹

⁵¹ <https://thedailyplasma.blog/2017/02/20/the-maars-of-pinacate/>

Arizona Snowbowl and Sunset Crater (San Francisco Volcanic Field)

Figure 29 - This series of craters and parent mountain is far to the west near Flagstaff; the “showbowl” and nearby Sunset Craters, and others, have the particular appearance of very active regions. It is like a boiling or bubbling up. The field is semi-concentrated, but wide enough. We can get an idea of the general size of the underground plume, and this pattern repeats **at each of the sites**, except the Shiprock area.

Valles Caldera

Figure 30 - the Valles Caldera represents the single largest (and probably oldest) volcano in the area. It has been active many times, as seen with the knobby interior mountains inside the crater - itself the remnant of a primordial explosion. The extensive, and thick, lava field is visible to the right. The author sees no reason to think of this as electrovolcanic, as it has few to no features in common with the seminal example: Olympus Mons. This appears, to this author, like a traditional tectonic volcanism. That doesn't mean there is no electric flux encouraged by the plume, and perhaps the smaller peaks inside indicate this. But perhaps it just isn't the best example for electrogeology. Perhaps it is, if we could have more advanced data and evidence.

Ute Mountain Region

Figure 31 - Ute Mountain and nearby Cerro de la Olla. The field is several shields with a little bit of cinder cones, still a relatively large field, proximal to the Rocky Mountains.

Springfield Volcanic Field

Figure 32 - Another large, and relatively diffuse volcanic field, probably showing the overall size of the plume, or it moved along creating the oblong shape. Again we see mostly cinder cones and some rare shield volcanoes.

Shiprock - Clearly lacking an important component...

Figure 33 - Shiprock; now we see that there is something **distinctly missing** from the Shiprock region: proximal cinder cones and any evidence of general volcanism in the area. In fact, the nearby buttes and gorge formations are more geographically dominant; and yet the monadnock’s height is clearly the tallest feature. This is a problem for standard model geology.

Electro-volcanism

By electro-volcanism, we mean either: a) volcanism controlled or induced by atmospheric to Earth electrical (Birkeland) currents, particularly a solar forcing or in a PEMS model; or b) magma plumes acting concurrently to MHD signatures (indicating electrical currents or telluric currents) in the mantle, rising up, and transferring this electricity in generally ground-to-cloud (via ash) direction. The author does not mean the proposed alteration of the idea in Shiprock where a chunk of crust is uplifted by direct arc. The author supposes that new standards would be necessary for this activity to be included in the loose ‘definitions’ that have emerged in observation of Earth’s, Io’s, and Mars’ volcanism.

Mars

The best place, outside of Earth (which is highly tectonic), to start would be Mars as it has four of the largest “volcanoes” in the known Solar System⁵².

⁵² Figure 34 - Mars with elevation; credit: NASA

Particularly Olympus Mons defies standard model explanation. Separating it from the other three, which are obviously related (and which we can cover in a moment, easily), it is a clear anomaly. It stands as a Texas-sized monstrosity, and yet so gently sloping a visitor would scarcely notice its incline. It has no lava fields but one large shelf, which cannot be lava because its thickness is excessive, considering its shortness/brevity. But the fact remains that the crater itself defies known volcanism⁵³, and there are no tectonics or known core or mantle plumes to keep the volcano alive. Meaning - and straining credulity - that *in only this one place on all of Mars* - a sudden, extensive magma plume of no known electrodynamic origin appeared, and made a consistent effort of building the Solar System's largest mountain, and then stopped completely. And is silent in every way, including seismic.⁵⁴

Figure 35 - Olympus Mons vs. Earth's largest volcanoes; bear in mind Mars has a weak magnetosphere and no known plate tectonics; credit: Science News

Worst of all for the standard model, there is little to no macrovisual evidence for expected ash fields that would cross the planet from such an extensive monster, and little to no volcanic fields, as we saw in the southwest desert, or in all caldera systems on Earth. It simply defies basic logic. $\frac{1}{3}$ the mass of Earth, but a volcano larger than Mauna Loa or Tamu Masif. Yet it looks so convincingly volcanic, even the author would not dare say it isn't. Therefore, we reach back in time to the explanations of the ancients, and in this we see that Venus had direct connections - perhaps even arcing based on scalloping, with the surface of Mars. Now the linear relationship of the other "shield volcanoes" and the size of Olympus Mons makes some sense. Especially as it was said that Athena and Ares had three or four battles. A direct arc connection makes complete sense.

⁵³ Again see Symbols of an Alien Sky part 2, there is extensive discussion there about the comparisons between shield volcanism and Olympus Mons

⁵⁴ https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/1999/ast29apr99_1

Please remember that if one body is much larger and rotating at a different rate, without or without Mars' weak magnetosphere to rub against, there will be a net transformer effect. This is a N1:N2 effect of "turns" and more than likely will lead in this case to increased voltage. It would be expected then that some type of circuit connection would occur, particularly in the light that, actually, the arc can connect in dark mode in space, and then switch to glow mode within the atmosphere.

Please read the previous paragraph again, because while the Thornhill-Scott-Talbot team has identified the correct vector for these mountains (most likely), in their documentary, these two concepts have eluded the Thunderbolts Project, except (perhaps) Bruce Leybourne. It is important to notice that conservation of momentum is an absolute kinetic reality. If an object stops rotating in one direction, the entire system needs rebalancing. Even planetary gods would seem like Noah and family if a galaxy's rotation was altered or stopped, relative to the great fabric! If we then expect these effects, we can see why humans were so afraid of any changes to the night (or day) sky: sudden changes in dynamic or kinetic motion resulted in distinct alterations of the circuit.

More to the point, the breakdown voltage behaviors in the various atmosphere levels (of Earth) are, according to Matin/Uman, non-linear⁵⁵. They are not smooth transitions. Which means benign changes acting as charge tsunamis may look miniscule or harmless in space, but as they approach Earth slow down, increase amplitude, and that could mean voltage, current, *or both*. As the impedance or reluctance drops, and the permittivity and conductance increase, the planet itself might add to the connection just as ground responds to "feeder" or "feeler" lightning bolts, once an established connection is made.

Then a multi-stroke arc connection can pump charge through the plasma-ion channel, delivering or extracting energy from the surface. In this case, the anode was Olympus Mons, and as the ground-to-space connection was made, it was maintained in an AC relationship long enough between Venus and Mars that the atmosphere was probably taken, and the planet transformed.

The point is that these connections are part of the electrogeological model for how the volcanoes formed, as well as the craters, rilles, gorges (without water), and the entire excavated northern hemisphere! Moreover these and the cathode craters will form gravity and magnetic anomalies, including abnormally low (sequestered charge) areas and concentrated (deposited charge) areas. All of these features will directly explain Martian geology, as well as many other mysteries of blue spherules⁵⁶, planet wide dust storms, self-cleaning rovers⁵⁷, etc. while a tectonic-less and dead planet⁵⁸ will not.

Io

But where do we see a non-Earthen system with this kind of example set? Now we turn to the Solar System's most volcanically active body: Jupiter's moon Io⁵⁹. Io has long been understood to be far too small to have as much volcanism as it has⁶⁰. Long before the advent of The Electric Universe and the rise of MHD as a dominant astronomical tool, a mechanism was sought. How it was done was to assume *gravitic* and kinetic energy, via tidal forces⁶¹ provided the motion in the proposed plates and/or a stretching of the shape of the moon. This is probably at least partially true. However, since then in MHD calculations have been made and

⁵⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/lightning-research>

⁵⁶ <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/64824> hematite; a magnetic material. Remnant of EDM activity

⁵⁷ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/nasa-rover-opportunities-selfie-shows-clean-machine>

⁵⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marsquake>

⁵⁹ <https://www.space.com/16419-io-facts-about-jupiters-volcanic-moon.html>

⁶⁰

<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/article/most-volcanic-world-in-solar-system-io-moon-still-mysterious-new-atlas-shows>

⁶¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tidal_heating_of_Io

confirmation as well, as to 'flux tube' (Birkeland Current) connections between Io and Jupiter. It is now quite well understood that the connection is profound. Furthermore, it is our 'smoking gun' proof of electro volcanism of the first kind. There are definite signs of plumes in the thin atmosphere, and a regular turnover of the crust due to continual lava extrusion. As such, it is pretty much a done deal, as far as the author is concerned. All that remains is the same work to do on Earth: place special charge measuring probes⁶² while modeling for BC's, and use magnetism to determine the relative strength of these currents⁶³. Until this is done, and compared with, say, the Sun's solar wind/flux⁶⁴ and known electric field⁶⁵ - now that they acknowledge what the EU was saying for 50+ years⁶⁶ - there won't be much more progress than the author here has described. It is our conjecture in PEMC that the **BC's supply the main source of energy for the magma plumes and volcanism**, and electro-tidal forces are also involved, and cannot be ignored. But they would be even less important, the author thinks, than the *magnetospheric induction* surrounding the moon's iron mantle⁶⁷ in constant relative motion around host planet Jupiter.

Enceladus

This is another moon, Saturn's ice moon with tremendous amounts of the polar molecule water⁶⁸. As such, it isn't too surprising that there are what are termed cryovolcanoes, not like Iceland, but with actual plumes of charged water⁶⁹. More to the point, these are more obviously related to PEMF activity. It is not reasonable to describe any of this using gravity, as they are clearly not 'geysers', and besides, geysers are hot volcanic⁷⁰. That isn't what we see on Enceladus.

Venus

Venus was once the core of Saturn⁷¹, or perhaps was ejected as extrusion of a liquid metallic hydrogen lattice⁷² due to the electrical stressing event⁷³. This is worldwide testimony, the best of which is direct and straightforward in Nahuatl myths surrounding Quetzlcoatl⁷⁴. At any rate, Venus has extremely large volcanoes⁷⁵ that match pretty well with the expected diameter and order of magnitude with those on Mars. This is very useful. Unfortunately, that's all we know. Literally the only probe that has been to the surface couldn't survive more than a few minutes⁷⁶, and so there is no further data than surface data. There are 3D scans, but that is not sampling, and probably is not reliable, to be blunt about it.

⁶² <https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/abs/2021/06/aa39298-20/aa39298-20.html>

⁶³ <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/1538-4365/ab4ff1>

⁶⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/science/solar-wind>

⁶⁵ <https://now.uiowa.edu/2021/07/physicists-led-university-iowa-more-fully-describe-suns-electric-field>

⁶⁶ Alfvén-Jeurgens-Scott (and Thornhill)

⁶⁷ <https://moon.nasa.gov/inside-and-out/what-is-inside-the-moon>

⁶⁸ <https://www.upr.org/science/2019-05-29/which-world-in-our-solar-system-has-the-most-water>

⁶⁹ <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jp202652g>

⁷⁰ <https://www.usgs.gov/news/geysers-what-exactly-are-they-made>

⁷¹ Multiple myths worldwide concern this; this is where Dr. Velikovsky was wrong to trust the Greek origins of Venus

⁷² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=080YgC45EJ8>

⁷³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

⁷⁴ <https://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

⁷⁵ Maat Mons: 8km tall, 395km diameter; Ascraeus Mons 18km tall, 480km in diameter; both are the 2nd largest on their respective planets.

⁷⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Venera>

However, setting aside volcanism, there are some interesting facts about Venus and Earth, in terms of relative ratios of orbit⁷⁷, and reasons to suspect that there is still some charge of attraction with Earth. There is even evidence that Sahara's sands come from Venus⁷⁸! This might mean that not only did Earth have a Saturnian origin, but it is possible that the motion of Earth from Saturn to Jupiter helped 'birth' Venus, and from Earth to the Sun may have caused Venus to move to orbit around the Sun. All, a big "perhaps". There is no way to scientifically validate this aspect of the breakdown, and everything relies on the newer myths from the time of the Mahabharata til now.

The reality is that we don't yet have the resources, in terms of manpower, in EPEMC to determine this data conclusively. But, even without AI, we can probably have a relative answer within 20-30 years. Nevertheless, it wouldn't be conclusive, and this is because of the Three Body Problem⁷⁹. Technically there were two 3BP's:

- ❖ The Saturn-Jupiter-Neptune triad, pre LaGrange Arrangement (Golden Age of the Gods)
 - Technically proto-Saturn at first and perhaps proto-Jupiter, although we don't know it birthed anything new. Proto-Saturn birthed Neptune⁸⁰ and Venus, at least.
- ❖ Venus-Earth-Mars (ignoring Mercury, which is supposed to have gone as emissary from Zeus/Jupiter to Apollo/Sol; and ignoring the Moon/Watcher⁸¹)

These conjunctions can never last, because they are inherently chaotic. However, they do provide opportunities for electrical behaviors, and for also ratios and connections to form which leave trace evidence (such as Mar's planet wide dust storms happening when it and Earth are in closest apogee⁸²). Finally, when the conjunctions end, there are destructive processes, and leftover charge related issues. Presumably these are implicated in some X% of meteorological phenomena on Earth, and Y% on Venus. Mar's only major phenomenon other than sandstorms are extremely tall dust devil vortices⁸³, which indicate clear BC connection behaviors, since there is no other weather to ostensibly form them. In truth, charge is also the cause of cyclones/vortices on Earth. But Earth's systems are complicated. Mars is much less so. Venus is opaque... for now.

Mercury and the Moon

Mercury and the Moon are clearly Jovian bodies, when you compare their surfaces with Jupiter's largest moons. Also, the Mesopotamian mythic texts agree, and probably the Moon is Innana, while Ishtar is actually Venus. Nevertheless, the former objects have zero volcanism. Rather, they have EDM evidence, and are useful in comparisons with the Barringer Crater. They have obviously bombarded surfaces, but the Moon in particular has a side facing Earth, which is EDM etched⁸⁴, and covered in polygonal craters, rilles⁸⁵, and crater-chains, which are signs of sputtering discharge. More to the point, there are no lava tubes (only rilles

⁷⁷ "In addition, Venus orbits the Sun in 224.695 days while Earth orbits the Sun in 365.242 days, creating a ratio of 8/13 (both Fibonacci numbers) or 0.615 (roughly phi.) Thus 5 conjunctions of Earth and Venus occur every 8 orbits of the Earth around the Sun and every 13 orbits of Venus" <https://www.goldennumber.net/solar-system>

⁷⁸ https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1 Appendix B; pp. 49-50

⁷⁹ "Addendum 2" Ibid.

⁸⁰ See: "Nazca Meme Cat" earthwork, discovered in 2020

⁸¹ Enuma Elish tablet 5

⁸² A direct admittal of electro static relationship; definitely not gravitic
<https://hubblesite.org/contents/news-releases/2005/news-2005-34.html>

⁸³ https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/MRO/news/mro20120404.html 12 miles!!

⁸⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pD69C7bAfis>

⁸⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DRvm28xbE00>

with scalloping, and rays), and definitely no way to explain all of them with any method other than EDM. You cannot get continuously shiny craters via impact. The EDM continues, to this day. As for Mercury, it is impacted a lot as well (as the back side of the Moon), but that's to be expected being so close to the sun. Our main curiosity should be in looking to Mercury for examples for polygonal cratering, which is a clear sign of EDM. But, the author is disinterested as compared to the previous bodies mentioned.

Lightning in Plumes

As for the second form of electrovolcanism, we unfortunately must infer the activity of charge within the magma plume from three [likely] facts:

1. There is not enough kinetic friction to describe why *some* ash plumes have intense volcanism. Otherwise, they all would need it. There's no reason to assume significantly different amounts of friction in different ash plumes, so different levels of static discharge. The plumes are moving minerals and ions... they are electric!
2. When solar forcing is related to hurricane activity, and possibly to sun-activated volcanism on the Canary Islands, we see wide vein activity (maybe).
3. Magma, being nickel-iron in motion, is inherently somewhat electrical, and charges are in definite motion, even if the flux is low. Therefore there may be a form of circuit connecting core or deep mantle charge reservoirs to the atmosphere (and beyond?).

Figure 36 - Lightning in Plume of Mt. Chalbuco; credit: F. Negroni⁸⁶

Figure 37 - Volcanic Lightning “the Glitch” ([gif](#))

The lightning in these plumes is rather like “heat lightning” related to summer season but in cold upper layers. More to the point, the charge and optical/IR energy behaviors are likely sequelae of the BC behaviors. But although we do not at present understand the BC's via direct sampling, we can simulate or reproduce it in a lab. We can look at Andy Hall's more comprehensive theory^{87 88}, and even if we do not adopt it in its entirety (full giant cyclone hypothesis), we can at least see the macro effects and the demonstration of hundreds of thousands to millions, or even billions of years (plausibly), of catastrophic jolts forward in the uniformitarian/calm stratigraphy. There is layering deposition and typical erosion, plate tectonics, and kinetic earthquakes. However, those are **not the only mechanisms to cause energy deposition and**

necessitate release. In all systems there are heat/optics, sound, electricity, magnetism, and

⁸⁶ <https://ourworldinfocus.com/past-photo-contest-winners/the-perfect-moment-photo-contest-winners/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ITvK1wyptU>

⁸⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yccR12vDJM&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UehsUgqCFIITvKKgJL5Niw1>

mechanics/kinetics. Together there is a total meteorological and geological dynamics (MGD), which is described partially in the PEMS paper, and will be more described in the sequel paper⁸⁹, forthcoming. However, MGD is not a well explored subject, even in the altstream, and until the author writes that sequel which will provide definitive or near definitive evidence, this paper will have to rely on Hall's evidentiary and empirical hypotheses.

Hall Theory & Combined Morphologies

The main evidence that is absolute and incontrovertible is the waveform (mostly triangular, but also arced and other waveforms indicating destructive interference and turbulence), that layers hard granite rock into shapes that are **impossible** through stratigraphy and fluvial erosion. The biblical messages about the Lord creating mountains and valleys, or making hills skip, are correlative evidence; as are the native myths. But these images below are direct proof and can be considered a "smoking gun"⁹⁰:

Triangular waveforms channel winds

6/17/16 Andrew Hall 6.15.16 208

Expansion and compression

6/17/16 Andrew Hall 6.15.16 215

Mainstream theory

- Waves cause faulting
- Fault blocks are realigned by surface waves - Love Wave
- Fault blocks compressed and expanded by surface waves - Rayleigh Wave

6/17/16 Andrew Hall 6.15.16 217

Chaos and coherence

6/17/16 Andrew Hall 6.15.16 227

Figures 38-41 - "arc-blasted Earth" slides (2016); credit: A. Hall

The key to understanding his hypothesis is that there are **known wave behaviors from empirically observed experiment**, and this is a specialized science that the mainstream of geology knows little about. But

⁸⁹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UxHBCUcO6nB1jYI-Ar5O3QipgWb4LfcDcmHewyNLM/edit?usp=sharing>

⁹⁰ Just as the octagon earthworks, the Ramesses Stele, the Columbia Rock Art, and the Perattian Thunderbolt at Big Sink

once you see these formations, you know they are impossible to be fluvial due to the above mentioned shock theories of rolling seismic waves. They are layered *from above*, not uplifted from below. They are plastered layers caused by triangular waveform deposition in coherent waves. Not sudden expansion and compression of earthquakes!

Figures 42 & 43: Comparing earthquake shocking⁹¹ (expansion and compression) with wave cancellation due to wind.

Figure 44 - Harmonic Reflections: again examples of sonic shock resonance from winds over a relatively short period of time, not from earthquakes over millions of years (separate incidents).

⁹¹ Not ironically the normal shocks probably were caused electrically, but Iran's cataclysms need more exploration.

Hole in wave-form

6/17/16

Andrew Hall 6.15.16

240

Hole in Iran

6/17/16

Andrew Hall 6.15.16

242

Figures 45 & 46: Comparing acoustic waveform experiment with keystone level geological evidence in Iran.

Expansion fan

6/17/16

Andrew Hall 6.15.16

259

Figure 47 - Expansion fans equate to more impossible to explain formations using standard geology

From these morphologies we see greater credence can be given to his larger hypotheses in the following images from his presentations. They provide some distinct evidence that he is *likely* correct about bigger formations⁹².

⁹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pt6NscQ2qS8>

After this we see that, indeed, his “crooked smile” evidence, provided first by Billy Yelverton, if not others, in situ (lab), has the weight and heft of Thor’s hammer Mjolnir itself!

Figure 48 - “the Crooked Smile” formation (Yelverton’s lab work); credit: A. Hall⁹³

These various morphologies aren’t quite “buffet” choosing, but more or less you can cherry pick from among them for your EPEMC hypothesis. For the HEGEME+PEMS hypothesis, we could theoretically adopt the entire Hall theorem. However, the author’s intuition is that it may be either very correct (more than he has grasped), and in fact under-represented worldwide, or very wrong because the catastrophism is too one-event minded and not uniformitarian *enough*, meaning that lots of these events happen, and together could indicate more. For example, the Kentucky/Tennessee/Virginia “crooked smile” (Pine Mountain)... surely that wasn’t the same vortex or another concurrent one?

Yet the deposition in Utah’s and Iran’s ranges suggests a long term **sustained** high temperature wind. It isn’t mere *puttification* of stone, it is consistent rock layering from a high velocity wind. The wind or breath of God (ru’ach), it would seem. But it is also not provable to come from the same cataclysmic era as we discuss in EPEMC, but could be prehistoric, aka pre-Atlantean and primeval. It could come from the days of Earth’s very formation inside or proximal (very) to Shamash! This is why we must not rush too headlong into adopting the entire Hall theory, though Navajo testimony supports it *somewhat*. It is hard to imagine anyone surviving, even under cliff faces, in such conditions.

⁹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdfBGqWpW5w>

An on Earth example of this will be published by this author in 2022; it has to do with aforementioned Pine Mountain flow.

Canary Islands, Living Examples of Solar Forcing?

If we shift back to Earth, we have to ask ourselves if there are live examples of electric induced catastrophe happening today, right now. In 2017 there was the much documented double X-class flare+3 hurricane event, where the chronology definitively showed that the hurricanes were pulling down energy from the sun and the sun's flares increased the strengths of the hurricanes. That thunderstorms, supercells, and cyclones are electrical has been discussed by the author elsewhere, as well as Leybourne, Thornhill, Hall, Clarage, Scott, and many others. It isn't exactly rocket science⁹⁴ to note that lightning indicates the presence of electrical behavior. And the plate-capacitance and rotation inductance (capacitance of current) is pretty obvious.

But could there be another event? The author contends that indeed the solar forced events of September 19, 2021 to December 13, 2021, with the sudden eruptions in the Canary Islands at the Cumbre Vieja ridge at La Palma, was just such an event. It has mostly been forgotten in the media since no landslide + megatsunami occurred, however, it was fairly continuous and powerful. There were concurrent rises in sunspot activity and therefore flares, as well. In general 2021 had only 64 days of spotlessness, versus 208 in 2020, and 281 in 2019, and 221 in 2018. Consider that in 2015 it had 0 days of spotlessness, and we see that indeed the sun had gone quiet for a while. In 2017 there were only 104, and in 2016 there were 32 days. Whatever caused this quietness is now over. In 2022 there have been 0 days without spots.

According to spaceweather.com on Sep. 19, 2021 there was a B1 class solar flare at 1602 UT⁹⁵. On the 20th, the following is reported,

“SOLAR STORM CLOUD: A storm is brewing on the sun. High above sunspot AR2871, magnetized clouds of plasma are swirling in a tempest more than 300,000 km wide.”

On the 21st, the following is reported:

“GLANCING BLOW CME, INCOMING: A dark filament of magnetism exploded away from the sun's southern hemisphere on Sept. 19th. [Watch the movie](#). NOAA analysts say the debris could reach Earth on Sept. 23rd in the form of a weak CME. A likely glancing blow could spark minor [G1-class geomagnetic storms](#)” (sic)

Could the Earth have established a connection on the 18th, and then as the sunspot rotated to view, drawn more power increasingly? It no longer seems implausible. The author recommends a deep study of the data be made by the volcanologists with no bias, and examine the data closely, as was done by meteorologists and MGD specialists post September 2017. As well as look at the facts around how often Fall results in such catastrophic events. Consider the facts of COVID-19, for example. This is not a trivial matter, and flippant dismissals are *unacceptable*. People's lives literally hang in the balance.

Figure 49 ([gif](#)) - September 28, 2018, Band Seventeen performed for the last time in Indonesia as dramatic footage of the tsunami that took 4,340 lives burst into the concert. It claimed all but the band leader's life, including his wife. There was no warning system, despite the 2004 Boxing Day tsunami disaster. Though there were no proximal sunspots or solar flares just prior to this, the region is home to the projected area where the

⁹⁴ Unironically they use rockets in lightning physics.

⁹⁵ <https://www.spaceweather.com/archive.php?view=1&day=19&month=09&year=2021>

magnetic poles now race, and is a high event subduction zone with typical volcanism, as well. Perhaps a deep study of Davidson's "Earthspots" may reveal other forms of low pressure zone proximal evidence. According to the USGS⁹⁶ there were multiple 10km deep 'blot echoes' hours before the 7.5 event at 10:02 UTC. Perhaps Davidson-Uyen models could have prevented a catastrophe from being as deadly, if the mainstream gave it a try. Certainly installing a tsunami warning system after 2004 would have been wise. Credit: Al-Jazeera

Shiprock vs. Barringer Crater

Under the conditions of continuous arc, since the facts of the site are clearly different from the conditions which created the Barringer Crater, can this site be qualified as a new form of electrovolcano? If the site is a matter of the ancient plume attracting an arc, might there be a reason to suspect that the Shiprock itself, and not the veins, could actually be raised magma/lava, uplifted in a sharp upthrust (similar as per the Patagonia and Utah ranges)? The author is not convinced, however, there is far too little lab data with extremely good controls to say for certain either way what processes were happening. However the author hopes to rectify that by 2023.

Nevertheless, we should compare and contrast the electrogeological facts of the two sites, if those facts are relatively known:

- One is anode, one 'cathode' or EDM.
- One is cryptoexplosive in a short manner, perhaps a nearly single arc; the other continuous for a time.
- One appears definitely of the Jovian era, and is relatively small in scale; the other from the YDE or other previous event related to the Shamash star destruction.
 - Typical dating for archaic indians puts them here post YDE, but that has been challenged by other newer sites. Sadly carbon dating is not reliable in the wake of Structured Atomic Model and PEM lab work showing transmutation (rearrangement) is commonplace.
- One appears to be polygonal, and the other upthrust related.
- **Neither** is volcanic.
- Shiprock appears to potentially be a very alternative form of electrovolcanism.
- Neither is electrovolcanic in the sense that we currently mean it.
- Both are catastrophic, but of different energetic scales.
- One may indicate a Hall event (Shiprock); the other a relatively common occurrence in the Zeus myths.

⁹⁶

<https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/map/?currentFeatureId=us1000h3p4&extent=-89.00782,-157.5&extent=89.00782,517.5&range=search&timeZone=utc&search=%7B%22name%22:%22Search%20Results%22,%22params%22:%7B%22starttime%22:%222018-09-28%2000:00:00%22,%22endtime%22:%222018-09-28%2023:59:59%22,%22minmagnitude%22:2.5,%22maxmagnitude%22:10,%22orderby%22:%22time%22%7D%7D>

- Both may be a “smoking gun”, but only Shiprock presently can be considered as such, given the vast conflicting data on Barringer Crater.

Conclusions

In short, Shiprock is **definitely not volcanic**, at least in traditional terms. The “meteor crater” is more than 50% likely to not be a bolide, but instead a EDM direct arc event, probably Jovian. However, more direct study needs to be conducted, and unfortunately, the site is privately held and commercially dependent on the meteor impact idea (currently).

With regards to electrovolcanism, the entire geological community would need a massive, Earth-shattering paradigm shift to be ready to consider it. However, if they understood Structured Atomic Model⁹⁷ v1.1⁹⁸ or 2.0 (Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis⁹⁹) then they would be more easily accepting of the problems of carbon¹⁰⁰ dating, rock dating¹⁰¹, and uniformitarianism¹⁰² as a whole. Also they would be more likely to accept the bare facts of atomic and isotopic transmutation. It isn't their fault: the dearth of knowledge about electromagnetism throughout the scientific corpus. It is, however, their problem.

In short, it was a very worthwhile trip.

⁹⁷ <http://ikkem.com/iccf23/orppt/ICCF23-OA-04%20Kaal.pdf>

⁹⁸ <https://www.amazon.com/Nature-Atom-Introduction-Structured-Model/dp/1838128026>

⁹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

¹⁰⁰

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Structured-Atom-Model-SAM-of-Carbon-with-12-protons-and-six-inner-electrons-between-the_fig1_350512889

¹⁰¹ <https://www.nature.com/scitable/knowledge/library/dating-rocks-and-fossils-using-geologic-methods-107924044/>

¹⁰² <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/uniformitarianism/>

References

1. Monadnock geology," Encyclopedia Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopedia, 2007
<https://www.britannica.com/science/monadnock>
2. "The Ship Rock landform," New Mexico Bureau of Geology & Mineral Resources, 2022,
<https://geoinfo.nmt.edu/tour/landmarks/shiprock/home.html#:~:text=Ship%20Rock%2C%20known%20as%20Tse,many%20thin%20veins%20of%20lava>
3. "Shiprock," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shiprock>
4. "Lava tube," U.S. Department of the Interior | U.S. Geological Survey, 2015,
https://volcanoes.usgs.gov/vsc/glossary/lava_tube.html
5. "Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge,"Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge
6. "Electric Universe Geology -- A New Beginning | Space News," Youtube, A. Hall/Thunderbolts Project, 2016,
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPcF40vBqzs>
7. "Soil Survey of Shiprock Area, Arizona and Apache County, Parts of San Juan County, New Mexico." United States Department of Agriculture Natural Resources Conservation Service, 1992,
https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/Internet/FSE_MANUSCRIPTS/new_mexico/NM717/0/Shiprock.pdf
8. " A Summary of the Engineering Assessment of Inactive Uranium Mill Tailings," Ford, ShipRock Site, Shiprock, New Mexico, Bacon & Davis, Inc., 1981, <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/6075949>
9. "Uranium-Bearing Evaporite Mineralization Influencing Plume Persistence: Literature Review and DOE-LM Site Surveys," US Department of Energy/Environmental Sciences Lab," 2016,
https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/2016/05/f31/AST_S13437.pdf
10. "Radiological Assessment of Stained Soils at the Monument Valley, Arizona, Processing Site," Department of Energy Office of Legacy Management, To the: US Nuclear Regulatory Commision, R. P. Bush, 2010,
<https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1025/ML102560402.pdf>
11. "Breaking petrified mud easily, Sf. R. careaga, 2022, <https://makeagif.com/i/3Ojnms>
12. "Plasmaglyphs Part 4," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.academia.edu/69494984/Plasmaglyphs_Part_4
13. " The Story of The Emergence," Sacred Texts, Native American Navajo,
<https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/nav/ncm/ncm4.htm>
14. "Winged Monster," The Tony Hillerman Portal, 2013,
<https://ehillerman.unm.edu/node/2255#sthash.urDlzEDM.dpbs>
15. "Impact Mechanics at Meteor Crater Arizona," Prepared on behalf of the U. S. Atomic Energy Commission and published with the permission of the Commission, E.M. Shoemaker, 1928,
<https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/1959/0108/report.pdf>
16. "Condensed Matter > Other Condensed Matter: IMPACT," Arxiv.com. D. Lohse et al., 2004,
<https://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0406368>
17. "Instant Fossilization," Youtube, P.M. Jupp/ Thunderbolts Project, EU2017,
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5vOMGQTjW9k&t=1s>
18. "Symbols of an Alien Sky, Episode 2: The Lightning Scarred Planet Mars," Youtube, Thunderbolts Project,
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y
19. "Appendix A & B - Plates," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga,
https://www.academia.edu/69494987/Appendix_A_and_B_Plates
20. "Why must a solar forcing be larger than a CO2 forcing to cause the same global mean surface temperature change?," Environmental Research Letters, Volume 11, Number 4, A. Modak et al 2016,
<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/11/4/044013>
21. "The Keystone Pattern," Youtube, A. Hall/ Thunderbolts Project, 2022,
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdfBGqWpW5w>

22. "Preliminary thorium daughter contour map and profiles of the Hicks Dome area, Hardin County, Illinois," United States Department of the Interior Geological Survey, J.A. Pitkin, 1974, <https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/1974/0157/report.pdf>
23. "Mineral Resources of the Illinois-Kentucky Mining District," US Department of the Interior, D. M. Pinckney, 1976, <https://pubs.usgs.gov/pp/0970/report.pdf>
24. "Structure of the Reelfoot-Rough Creek Rift System, Fluorspar Area Fault Complex, and Hicks Dome, Southern Illinois and Western Kentucky— New Constraints from Regional Seismic Reflection Data," US Department of the Interior, C. J. Potter et al, 1995, <https://pubs.usgs.gov/pp/1538q/report.pdf>
25. "Garden of the Gods Bizarre Bands," <https://shawneenf.occ.edu/en/24-garden-of-the-gods-bizarre-bands-55873.html>
26. "Could so-called "Dark Matter" really be Spiritual matter?????" LDS Freedom Forum, Ashley B., 2011, <https://www.ldsfreedomforum.com/viewtopic.php?t=17155&start=30>
27. "Tektite Geology," Encyclopedia Britannica, 2018, <https://www.britannica.com/science/tektite>
28. "Tektite Meaning and Properties," Fire Mountain Gems, <https://www.firemountaingems.com/resources/encyclopedia/gem-notes/ha5r>
29. "Electrogeologist," (EPEMC) Gateway. Sf. R. Careaga, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/a-hall>
30. "The Arc-Blasted Earth: EU2016," Youtube/ Thunderbolts Project, A. Hall, 2017, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM&t=2187s>
31. "Creator's Second Hand | EU2015," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, E. Bagashov, 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LsItU6getrY>
32. "The Jupiter-Io Connection: An Alfvén Engine in Space," Science New Series, Vol. 238, No. 4824, J.W. Belcher, 1987, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1700040>
33. "Electrical Circuit Between Saturn and Enceladus," NASA, 2011, <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/resources/15289/electrical-circuit-between-saturn-and-enceladus/>
34. "Enceladus: An Active Cryovolcanic Satellite," Saturn from Cassini-Huygens, J.R. Spencer et al, 2009, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4020-9217-6_21
35. "Vortices and Flux Ropes in Electron MHD Plasmas I." Published, Physica Scripta T84, R. L. Stenzel, J. M. Urrutia & M. C. Giskey, 2000, <https://www.physics.ucla.edu/plasma-exp/references/publications/PhysScripta/ITCPP99rls1preprint.pdf>
36. "Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond," Wiley.com., A. Keiling et al, 2018, <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Electric+Currents+in+Geospace+and+Beyond-p-9781119324492>
37. "Magnetic Universe Theory A Top-Down Review of Phases of Magnetic Theory Development, with accompanying historiography and comparison with Unified/Aether Field Theories including EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC
38. See also the works of Donald Scott and Wal Thornhill from "The Electric Sky" to "The Electric Universe" books.
39. "NASA's Juno Navigators Enable Jupiter Cyclone Discovery," NASA Jet Propulsion Lab, 2019, <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/nasas-juno-navigators-enable-jupiter-cyclone-discovery>
40. "The 'Great' Conjunction of Jupiter and Saturn," NASA Solar System and Beyond, 2020, <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/the-great-conjunction-of-jupiter-and-saturn>
41. "Addendum 2: Megafauna Extinction Events Update to the Thunderbolt Extinction Model; the Surprising truth of the Younger Dryas Event that Changes Everything," Research Gate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything
42. "Maar," USGS, <https://volcanoes.usgs.gov/vsc/glossary/maar.html>

43. : The Maars of Pinacate," The Daily Plasma/Thunder Blogs, Re-posted courtesy of Thunderbolts.info, 2017, <https://thedailyplasma.blog/2017/02/20/the-maars-of-pinacate/>
44. Again see Symbols of an Alien Sky part 2, there is extensive discussion there about the comparisons between shield volcanism and Olympus Mons
45. "Plate Tectonics on Mars?" NASA Science, 1999, https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/1999/ast29apr99_1
46. "Hematite Spherules on Mars," Mineralogy, A. K. Misra & T. E. Acosta-Maeda, 2018, <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/64824>
47. "NASA Rover Opportunity's Selfie Shows Clean Machine," NASA, Jet Propulsion Lab, 2014, <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/nasa-rover-opportunitys-selfie-shows-clean-machine>
48. "Marsquake," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marsquake>
49. "Io: A guide to Jupiter's volcanic moon," Space.com., D. Dobrijevic, 2022, <https://www.space.com/16419-io-facts-about-jupiters-volcanic-moon.html>
50. "This is our best look yet at the solar system's most volcanic object," Nat Geo, R.G. Andrews, 2019, <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/article/most-volcanic-world-in-solar-system-io-moon-still-mysterious-new-atlas-shows>
51. "Tidal heating of Io," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tidal_heating_of_Io
52. "Detection of small magnetic flux ropes from the third and fourth Parker Solar Probe encounters," Astronomy and Physics, L.L. Zhao et al, 2021, <https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/abs/2021/06/aa39298-20/aa39298-20.html>
53. "Identification of Magnetic Flux Ropes from Parker Solar Probe Observations during the First Encounter," The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series, L. L. Zhao et al, 2020, <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/1538-4365/ab4ff1>
54. "Solar Wind Astronomy," Britannica Encyclopedia, 2019, <https://www.britannica.com/science/solar-wind>
55. "Physicists led by University of Iowa more fully describe sun's electric field," Iowa Now, R. C. Lewis, 2021, <https://now.uiowa.edu/2021/07/physicists-led-university-iowa-more-fully-describe-suns-electric-field>
56. Alfvén-Jeurgens-Scott (and Thornhill)
57. "Inside the Moon- Inside and Out," NASA, <https://moon.nasa.gov/inside-and-out/what-is-inside-the-moon/>
58. "Which World In Our Solar System Has The Most Water?," Utah Public Radio, T. Westre, 2019, <https://www.upr.org/science/2019-05-29/which-world-in-our-solar-system-has-the-most-water>
59. "Water with Excess Electric Charge," ACS Publications, L. P. Santos et al, 2011, <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jp202652q>
60. "Geysers—what exactly are they made of?," USGS, By Yellowstone Volcano Observatory, 2020, <https://www.usgs.gov/news/geysers-what-exactly-are-they-made>
61. "Experimental Supporting Evidence - Lattice Confinement Fusion Reactions & the Sun!," Youtube/Sky Scholar, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=080YgC45EJ8>
62. "Wal Thornhill: The Star 'Proto-Saturn' | EU Workshop," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytq0-8w
63. "The Death of Quetzalcōātl Anales de Cuauhtitlan (Codex Chimalpopoca, sections 5 to 8)" ucsd.com.,2020, <https://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>
64. "Venera," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Venera>
65. "Phi and the Solar System," Goldennumber.net Blog, G. Meisner, 2012, <https://www.goldennumber.net/solar-system/>
66. "Ashes of Atlantis - part 1," Appendix B; pp. 49-50, Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1
67. See: "Nazca Meme Cat" earthwork, discovered in 2020
68. Enuma Elish tablet 5
69. "Mars Kicks Up The Dust as It Makes Closest Approach to Earth," NASA Hubblesite, <https://hubblesite.org/contents/news-releases/2005/news-2005-34.html>
70. "12-Mile-High Martian Dust Devil Caught in Act," NASA News, 2012, https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/MRO/news/mro20120404.html
71. "Plasma Ray Craters," Youtube/See The Pattern,

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pD69C7bAfis>
72. "What Created Strange Rivers on the Moon?," Youtube/See The Pattern, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DRvm28xbE00>
73. "The Perfect Moment Photo Contest Winners," Our World in Focus, <https://ourworldinfocus.com/past-photo-contest-winners/the-perfect-moment-photo-contest-winners/>
74. "Andrew Hall: The Arc Blasted Earth | Space News," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ITvK1wyptU>
75. "Andrew Hall: Eye of the Electric Storm | Space News," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yccR12vDJM&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UehsUggCFIITvKKgLJ5Niw1>
76. "Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky 2.0," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UxHBiBCUcO6nB1jYI-Ar5O3QipgWb4LfcDcmHewyNLM/edit#heading=h.8o5c7ha1iirn>
77. "Andrew Hall: The Shocking Truth | Thunderbolts," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pt6NscQ2gS8>
78. "Andrew Hall: The Keystone Pattern | Thunderbolts," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdfBGqWpW5w>
79. "Time Machine," Space Weather.com, Sunday, Sept 21, 2019, <https://www.spaceweather.com/archive.php?view=1&day=19&month=09&year=2021>
80. "140 earthquakes." USGS, <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/map/?currentFeatureId=us1000h3p4&extent=-89.30492,-157.5&extent=89.29634,517.5&range=search&timeZone=utc&search=%7B%22name%22:%22Search%20Results%22,%22params%22:%7B%22starttime%22:%222018-09-28%2000:00:00%22,%22endtime%22:%222018-09-28%2023:59:59%22,%22minmagnitude%22:2.5%22maxmagnitude%22:10.%22orderby%22:%22time%22%7D%7D>
81. "The Explanatory Power of the Structured Atom Model (SAM)," J.E. Kaal et al, <http://ikkem.com/iccf23/orppt/ICCF23-OA-04%20Kaal.pdf>
82. "The Nature of the Atom: An Introduction to the Structured Atom Model," Amazon, J.E. Kall et al, 2021, <https://www.amazon.com/Nature-Atom-Introduction-Structured-Model/dp/1838128026>
83. "Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis
84. "SAM Model Image," Research Gate, C. Wynter, https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Structured-Atom-Model-SAM-of-Carbon-with-12-protons-and-six-inner-electrons-between-the_fig1_350512889
85. "Dating Rocks and Fossils Using Geologic Methods," Nature.com, D. J. Pepe & A. L. Deino, 2013, <https://www.nature.com/scitable/knowledge/library/dating-rocks-and-fossils-using-geologic-methods-107924044/>
86. "Uniformitarianism," Nat Geo, J. Hutton, <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/uniformitarianism>